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- P - Prototype
- DEC - Websites, Patent filing, Press & media actions, Videos, etc
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INTRODUCTION

This deliverable presents the second set of Virtual Access (VA) services integrated into the NEP infrastructure. These online services, all running on a virtual machine (4 CPUs, 16 GB RAM, 50 GB SDD, OS: Debian 11, SSL via Apache reverse proxy) hosted by the Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT), were developed within the Work Package (WP) 16 and were designed to improve the data FAIRness and to facilitate the user experience on (meta)data generation, post-processing or exploration.

The services are authenticated upon the NEP Single Sign-On (SSO) system via Keycloak [14]. The usage is monitored by aggregating the Units of Access (UoA), which are established to be every single action made by a logged-in user on one of the services, and monitored: whenever a logged-in user performs an action, the service backend sends a REST request to the NEP backend including the service ID and increases the usage counter by 1 UoA.

No information about the users is handled or stored by the services. The Keycloak token, used by the Single Sign-On, is the only piece of information needed to grant access to the service.

The document consists of three sections describing one VA service each. For completeness, each section explicitly mentions the corresponding WP16 task in which the service was framed and the deliverable in which it was described, if applicable.

Nuclear Magnetic Resonance data curation

Data curation is essential to improve Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR) correlation and spectral analysis. Many initiatives have already identified this need and have offered online databases [1-6], in addition to the ones locally maintained by individual institutes. However, these databases contain only a set of spectra related to a specific focus and often do not overlap with each other.

To overcome this issue, we developed the NMR Spectra Graph [7]. This service aims at offering a centralized Graphical User Interface (GUI) providing information in a uniform way about NMR resources and related data that are distributed over the internet. Using this service, the scientists can query for NMR spectral metadata on a single system and will no longer need to search in every separate database.

To deploy the service, we initially selected nmrXiv [1] and Biological Magnetic Resonance Data Bank [2], two online databases exposing a public Application Programming Interface (API) and thus allowing us to harvest the deposited NMR spectra. After a consultation with expert researchers in this field, the metadata of the spectra were then represented in a standardized format containing the most relevant information in terms of data location, experiment performed, molecules identified in the spectrum, provenance and related NMR resources.

The standardized format is based on the FAIR Digital Object (FDO) concept [8,9] and was adapted to an ontology based on W3C Semantic Web Standards [10]. The ontology was made actionable by transforming it into an RDF Triple-Store which can be queried using SPARQL [11]. To ease the users, we implemented and exposed a selected set of relevant queries on the service GUI. A description guides the user through the possible requests they can make on the NMR graph running in the backend. The required input is the set of metadata attributes based on which the graph should be queried (see Figure 1).

NMR Query interface

Submit Your Query

This graphical user interface enables one to search for NMR data resources across data bases (currently NMRXIV - <https://nmrxiv.org/> and BMRB - <https://bmrbl.io/>). Each data resource has been represented as a FAIR Digital NMR Object (FDO) that has a unique Persistent Identifier (PID) and a set of metadata to easily identify and characterize an NMR resource.

Please fill out either the first set of fields to query by a record attribute and OPTIONALLY corresponding value OR the PID field to query by the PID of a FDO. Do not fill both.

Query for a particular attribute and regex of a value that occur in an information record to display all matching attribute values and the corresponding PID of the FDO.

digitalObjectLocation

Query for a particular PID of a FDO to display all attributes and their values of its information record.

PID

Documentation

The following queries are enabled:

- To get a list of all PIDs in the graph database, insert *all* in the PID search field.
- Filter for data resource license (URL): *licenseURL*
- Filter for data resource contact information (email or ORCID): *contact*
- Filter for the data resource location attributes (URL): *digitalObjectLocation* or *landingPageLocation*
- Filter for date information attributes (YYYY-MM-DDThh:mm:ss.sssssZ): *dateCreated* or *dateModified*
- Filter for data base internal IDs (P_Id and S_Id): *projectIdentifier* or *sampleIdentifier*
- Filter for data resource format (Media-types): *containerMedia-type-IANA* or *media-type-IANA*

Messages

Information ✕

User demo@nffa.eu logged in.

Figure 1: NMR Graph query input

For example, a user would like to search for NMR data which have been stored across several storage systems; in this case, the user can insert the standardized metadata attribute "digitalObjectLocation", available for all NMR resources, in the Record Attribute field. The result of the query will be all the available NMR resources, as shown in Figure 2.

Results

Query Results for attribute: digitalObjectLocation

Request a new query

Attribute Value	PID of FAIR Digital Objects
https://s3.uni-jena.de/nmr/production/archive/00e2477-5d20-4c90-8e91-f922e0ca09/5a-cyprinol-sulfate-nmrshftb-datasets.zip	21.1152/894f69d-fc73-42a3-9efe-ddcae8ba96c
https://s3.uni-jena.de/nmr/production/archive/01564883-7955-4714-82dd-cb8d78b6cd3e/caripyrin.zip	21.1152/a700a0ce-6a29-4768-839a-0518610d7e7
https://s3.uni-jena.de/nmr/production/archive/02879197-c34f-46f9-97f9-1cd9541eb486/pulegon-die-polei-minze-im-wandel-der-zellen.zip	21.1152/9726ab25-4ec5-44d5-a3a2-a4e6fa639c
https://s3.uni-jena.de/nmr/production/archive/0a2224a1-2686-4e07-81c9-679f2d63b327/chinin-ein-legendares-alkaloid-nmrshftb-datasets.zip	21.1152/a98ed96-e24a-496e-bdca-aa2b586ab66
https://s3.uni-jena.de/nmr/production/archive/7219f1d-bf98-4f73-8101-29d2bba7e96/chlorophyll-nmrshftb-datasets.zip	21.1152/0f53834-79de-42ba-8b9b-1dc52af03e9d
https://s3.uni-jena.de/nmr/production/archive/7970bc33-f1de-46a8-9667-8f79be774c2/abwarten-und-baerentrundenbatter-tee-trinken-mit-arbutin-nmrshftb-datasets.zip	21.1152/bd9ba32-b001-4f5f-ab2c-838d760e1d28
https://s3.uni-jena.de/nmr/production/archive/26e63e01-4de1-46c8-8522-773146c4a25/thymochinon-das-gelbe-vom-ol-nmrshftb-datasets.zip	21.1152/0003e528-7e3e-4540-879b-a4e6027cc681
https://s3.uni-jena.de/nmr/production/archive/2d05156b-5359-4e7a-9c14-6fed5547665/cecaptrm.zip	21.1152/ca0c5dda-854e-4fe4-b215-c43991639006
https://s3.uni-jena.de/nmr/production/archive/2e7ba5ab-b810-4149-99a0-b1d48627ed4/classics-in-spectroscopy-isolation-and-structure-elucidation-of-natural-products-nmrshftb-datasets.zip	21.1152/ice17c9bd-de53-442b-b703-c0e69918af3d
https://s3.uni-jena.de/nmr/production/archive/3316a4d3-8c9a-4ba3-8257-8b3c13f33781/die-optischen-aufheiler-fraxin-und-aesculin-nmrshftb-datasets.zip	21.1152/6788b092-5ce8-4e99-8784-cdb70cb70634
https://s3.uni-jena.de/nmr/production/archive/4213621a-6af0-470d-abe8-5add99747902/karminsaeure.zip	21.1152/7631adef-4ee8-4a79-bf95-7a5980c0cb66
https://s3.uni-jena.de/nmr/production/archive/526b3e0b-f77c-4a75-bc84-f946a115c5e2/karminsaeure-nmrshftb-datasets.zip	21.1152/c10bb4bb-66d2-4ef8-

Messages

Information ✕

User demo@nffa.eu logged in.

Figure 2: NMR Graph query results for "Attribute": "digitalObjectLocation"

Additional regex terms may be included to refine the search, e.g. to filter for specific storage systems. The resulting table then contains a list of URLs where the NMR resources are deposited, as well as the corresponding identifiers (PIDs) of the associated Graph entries containing additional metadata attributes and descriptions. These PIDs could be used in a subsequent query to further explore the NMR metadata description, as shown in Figure 3.

The screenshot shows the NFFA-Europe Data Management and Virtual Access Service interface. At the top, it says "NFFA-Europe Data Management and Virtual Access Service" and "NMR Metadata Query and MRI Contrast Prediction". The user is logged in as "demo@nffa.eu". The main content area is titled "Query Results for FDO with PID: 21.11152/894ffe9d-fe73-42a3-9efe-ddcae8baf96c". Below this, there is a table with two columns: "Attribute" and "Attribute Value".

Attribute	Attribute Value
datasetIdentifier	D1565
datasetIdentifier	D1566
datasetIdentifier	D1567
datasetIdentifier	D1568
datasetIdentifier	D1569
datasetIdentifier	D1570
MedicalImageModality	NMR
projectIdentifier	P47
sampleIdentifier	S267
media-type-IANA	zip
dateCreated	2023-12-26T20:21:16.000000Z
dateModified	2023-12-26T20:29:29.000000Z
kernelInformationProfile	21.11148/20cab4d8e6f07348d173
containerMedia-type-IANA	application/xml
licenseURL	https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/legalcode
landingPageLocation	https://rnmrviv.org/P47

Below the table, there are three buttons: "Remove All", "Remove information", and "Remove Error". There is also a message box that says "Information User demo@nffa.eu logged in."

Figure 3: NMR Graph query results for "PID"

FDOs are primarily intended for machine-actionability and automation; nevertheless, the service provides the option to visualize the records using the FAIR-DOscope [12], a generic FDO viewer and browser which offers a tabular view of the contents in a human-readable format and a graphical representation of related FDOs. The resulting PIDs from a query (as the ones shown in Figure 3) can be used as input in the FAIR-DOscope [12] to visualize their content. Figure 4 shows how a given PID is intuitively represented in FAIR-DOscope.

The screenshot displays the FAIR-DOscope interface for a specific PID. At the top, the FAIR-DOscope logo and tagline 'Explore the facets of FAIR Digital Objects' are visible. Below the search bar, the PID '21.11152/894ffe9d-fe73-42a3-9efe-ddcae8ba96c' is entered. The interface is split into two main sections: a tabular view on the left and graphical representations on the right.

Left Panel: PID Information Record

Type	Value
kernelInformationProfile	21.111148/b9b76f887845e32d29f7
dateCreated	2023-12-26T20:21:16+00:00
dateModified	2023-12-26T20:28:29+00:00
licenseUrl	https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.
contact	http://noura.rayya@uni-jena.de
digitalObjectLocation	https://s3.uni-jena.de/hmrxiv/production/an
# checksum	{'sha256sum': 'bfb73e69b166f6eeaa197ed'
digitalObjectType	21.111148/20dab4d8e6f07348d173
HS_ADMIN	

Right Panel: Graphical Representations

- FDO Badge:** A small badge showing the PID and a 'Copy as' button.
- FAIR DO Graph:** A graph visualization showing a single node representing the PID.
- PID Component:** A component showing the PID and a 'Copy Code' button.

Messages Panel: A list of system messages with 'Remove All', 'Remove Information', and 'Remove Error' buttons.

- Information: Resolving new FDO with PID 21.11152/894ffe9d-fe73-42a3-9efe-ddcae8ba96c
- Information: Setting rendering to interactive mode.
- Information: Loading FDO from user-provided PID 21.11152/894ffe9d-fe73-42a3-9efe-ddcae8ba96c
- Information: Loading PID 21.11152/894ffe9d-fe73-42a3-9efe-ddcae8ba96c from query parameter.
- Information: Loaded 14 PIDs from history.

Figure 4: FAIR-DOscope tabular view of the information record in human-readable form (left) and the graphical representation of the related FDOs (right) for a given PID.

In the first months after the release of the service, we expect to collect feedback from the community: for instance, the current queries are provided as a starting point and new functionalities may be easily integrated upon request. Moreover, the NMR Graph can possibly be extended to integrate new databases (e.g., the Human Metabolome Database [3]) as well as internal NMR archives locally stored by individual institutes (e.g. at KIT-IMT). The chosen metadata format is appropriate to extend the service for potential future needs, e.g. to link NMR resources to both the experimental metadata and the software needed to analyze the NMR spectra.

The NMR Spectra Graph was developed as foreseen in the Subtask 16.2.4 "NMR Data Curation" of the WP16, and was described in the deliverable D16.4 [13].

Magnetic Resonance Image reconstruction and contrast prediction

Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) is applied in material sciences for non-invasive investigation of sample structure and composition, by leveraging the differences in tissue contrasts. However, every different type of contrast, encoded in the MR image, typically requires a separate measurement, which is a time-consuming task.

To tackle this issue, the MRI Prediction Service [15] was designed. The service offers a simple and intuitive GUI based on machine learning, which has the aim to optimize the information contained within the datasets measured in the same MRI experiment in order to predict an alternative contrast type from a given one. This decreases the measurement time by a factor n for each of the n contrast types that can be predicted.

The service, shown in Figure 5, allows users to upload a DICOM file obtained at a given contrast expressed in terms of the pulse sequence parameters TE and TR (echo time and repetition time, respectively) and to request a prediction of how the image would look like if measured with an alternative contrast, based on the given theoretical sequence parameters that would have been used.

The screenshot shows the MRI Prediction Service input page. At the top, there is a header with the NFFA logo and the text "NFFA-Europe Data Management and Virtual Access Service" and "NMR Metadata Query and MRI Contrast Prediction". A user is logged in as "demo@nffa.eu". The main content area is titled "MRI Prediction Interface" and "Submit Your DICOM file and parameters". It contains a file upload field with "series1.dcm", input fields for "Input image TE value: 5", "Input image TR value: 110", "Output image TE value: 5", and "Output image TR value: 800", and an "Upload" button. Below the form is a "Messages" section with buttons for "Remove All", "Remove Information", and "Remove Error". An information message states "User demo@nffa.eu logged in."

Figure 5: MRI Prediction Service input page

The resulting image is then displayed as in a preview and can be downloaded together with the corresponding theoretical sequence parameter used to generate it and the original DICOM file (Figure 6). In the case where one DICOM file contains multiple images, an alternative image is predicted for each, but only the first image in the stack is displayed to prevent possible conflicts with large datasets.

Figure 6: MRI prediction result

Currently, the machine learning model has been trained on predicting contrasts for a solution of CuSO_4 at different concentrations, as required by our target users. We are open to receive further input data from the community to train the model on different materials to further improve the applicability of the service.

The MRI Prediction Service was developed as foreseen in the Subtask 16.2.3 “MRI reconstruction and contrast prediction” of the WP16, and was described in the deliverable D16.4 [13].

Mapping Service

The Mapping Service [16] is a versatile tool designed to streamline the management of scientific research data. It addresses the critical need for standardized metadata by automatically extracting it from diverse experimental data files and mapping it to community-developed schemas which are registered in MetaRepo [17]. The Mapping Service features a user-friendly interface, pictured in Figure 7, and a modular plugin architecture designed to be easily extensible.

Figure 7: Mapping Service landing page.

The user is greeted with a short message which explains the main functions of the tool and links to the available documentation. The list of available mapping plugins is then presented and easily navigable with legible descriptions of each plugin. The user selects the plugin best suited to their data format and the generating instrument, is then prompted to upload their file, which is processed via the “Map document” button, triggering an automatic download of the results file. The output is a schema-adherent metadata document in JSON format, ensuring consistency, reusability, and interoperability of the research data and the metadata describing it.

The list of the available mapping plugins, together with the instrument vendors that are currently supported and the metadata schemas according to which the extracted metadata are mapped, are outlined in Table 1. In particular, the “MRI to JSON” plugin was presented and used in [18], while the “ThermoFisher SEM to JSON” was used to map the metadata of the SEM image [31] acquired and analyzed in [32], before registering it in MetaRepo [33].

Table 1: List of mapping plugins currently available in the Mapping Service, instrument vendors supported and references to the target metadata schemas to which the plugins map the metadata extracted from the data file.

MAPPING PLUGIN	SUPPORTED VENDOR	RELATED METADATA SCHEMA
Zeiss SEM to JSON	Zeiss	[19]
SEM to TXT	Zeiss	[19]
ThermoFisher SEM to JSON	ThermoFisher	[19]
SEM-FIB Tomography Acquisition to JSON	ThermoFisher	[20-22]
SEM-FIB Tomography Acquisition to TXT	ThermoFisher	[20-22]
MRI to JSON	DICOM	[23]

Some of the key benefits of the Mapping Service include:

- Elimination, or at least reduction, of manual metadata compilation: by automating the process, the Mapping Service not only reduces the time and effort required for metadata management, but it also mitigates the potential for human errors
- Extensible design: the Mapping Service readily accommodates new schemas and mappings for different experimental techniques
- Easy adoption: A web-based architecture requires no local installation or dependencies from end-users.

The functionalities and interface have been showcased at several conferences during its development, namely in the form of posters and talks [24-27]. Thanks to the discussions that arose during these events, we were able to integrate feedback received from researchers in the materials science field to improve the service and its user interface. Nevertheless, new plugins can be developed, if required by the community.

The Mapping Service can be included in the Task 16.4 "Scouting activities for further data services" of the WP16, as it was developed in order to facilitate the management and FAIRification of research data and to make interaction with the MetaRepo [20] more efficient.

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